

Physico-Chemical Studies of Emulsions of Mixed Oils with Surfactants as Emulsifying Agents

K. D. JAIN, MANJU GOEL and J. C. SHARMA

Department of Chemistry, D. A. V. (P. G.) College, Dehra Dun

and

AJAY K. JAIN

University of Roorkee, Roorkee

Manuscript received 23 June 1980, accepted 10 December 1982

Several O/W emulsions with water, kerosene, turpentine and olive oil as external and internal phases and sodium dodecyl sulphate needles (SDSN, anionic surfactant), cetyl trimethyl ammonium bromide (CTMAB, cationic surfactant) and polyoxyethylene sorbitan monostearate (Tween-60, nonionic surfactant) as emulsifying agents have been prepared. Physico-chemical properties like emulsion type, specific gravity, surface tension, pH, viscosity, conductivity and particle size have been studied. The emulsions of maximum stability are those which have low surface tension and specific gravity, and high conductivity, particle size and viscosity.

A wide variety of emulsions have been prepared by taking two immiscible liquids as external and internal phases stabilised by surface active materials¹⁻⁴. Various other emulsifying agents like naturally occurring substances⁵⁻⁶ and finely divided solids^{7,8} have been used. Various patents and papers using electrolytes^{9,10}, colloids¹¹, resin soaps¹², water soluble gums^{13,14}, organic compounds^{15,16}, sulphonic acids and sulphonated oils¹⁷ as surfactants have been mentioned in the literature.

Very little work on the chemistry of emulsions with respect to surfactants and their mixtures; binary mixtures like anionic+cationic, cationic+nonionic, nonionic+anionic surfactants, and tertiary mixtures like anionic+cationic+nonionic surfactants has been reported. Jain and Sharma¹⁸ studied stable emulsions of kerosene, turpentine and water with various single surfactants. In the present work attempts have been made to study the physico-chemical properties of emulsions by taking a single surfactant (anionic, cationic, nonionic) as emulsifying agent and water as continuous phase and mixed oils [kerosene (K)+turpentine (T); olive oil (OO)+kerosene (K); olive oil (OO)+turpentine (T)] as dispersed phase.

Experimental

Materials: Sodium dodecyl sulphate needles (SDSN) and cetyl trimethyl ammonium bromide (CTMAB), (both B.D.H.) were used as anionic and cationic surfactants, respectively while polyoxyethylene sorbitan monostearate (Tween-60) (Koch Light) as nonionic surfactant. Kerosene (b.p. 250°, sp. gr. 0.7746) was double distilled before use

while turpentine (b. p. 178°, sp. gr. 0.82142) and olive oil (b.p. 215°, sp. gr. 0.91083) were used as such. Water used was double-distilled, pH 6.1; conductivity 0.68×10^{-6} ohm⁻¹ cm⁻¹.

Preparation of emulsions: Emulsions were prepared by agent-in-oil method¹⁹ as follows:

- Different concentration of water and mixed oils, i.e. (K+T; T+OO; K+OO) and fixed concentration of emulsifying agent.
- Different concentration of emulsifying agent and fixed concentration of water and mixed oils.

To the aqueous solutions of surfactants, mixed oil was added with stirring and the mixture blended vigorously for 2 min in Gem Mixy homogeniser until thoroughly homogenised.

Properties of emulsions: Dye solubility method was used to determine the type of emulsion²⁰. Calcomine blue (soluble in water but insoluble in oils) and Savinyl green (soluble in oils but insoluble in water) were added to two separate parts of each emulsion. The resulting mixture was stirred gently. The part containing Calcomine blue immediately turned blue while the other part remained white, proving that the oils were in the dispersed and water in the continuous phase. It could thus be assumed that all the emulsions were oil-water type. Properties of the emulsions were studied at 30°.

A compound microscope was used to determine the particle size. Ostwald viscometer, pycnometer and drop weight method were used to determine the viscosity, specific gravity and surface tension of the emulsions, respectively. The pH

was measured by Beckman pH meter and conductivity with LBR/B (W.T.W., German) conductance meter. All observations were recorded at 30°. The results are summarised in Tables 1-6.

TABLE 1—EMULSION STABILISED BY ANIONIC SURFACTANT

Emulsion type : O/W ; SDSN = 0.05 g ; K + T = 5 ml each ; Temp. 30°

Sl. No.	Water ml	Ratio O/W	Specific gravity	Viscosity cp	Surface tension (dynes/cm)	Conductivity ($\times 10^{-8}$ ohms $^{-1}$ cm $^{-1}$)	pH	Particle size μ
1.	10	1/1	0.8918	4.120	14.06	24.5	6.65	10-11
2.	20	1/2	0.9289	2.754	14.28	16.0	6.66	9-10
3.	30	1/3	0.9814	1.690	14.81	15.8	6.6	8-9
4.	40	1/4	0.9408	1.591	14.87	14.5	6.55	8-9
5.	50	1/5	0.9550	1.531	14.41	12.9	6.5	7-8
6.	60	1/6	0.9592	1.495	14.49	11.5	6.8	7-8
7.	70	1/7	0.9694	1.451	14.53	10.5	6.25	6-7
8.	80	1/8	0.9685	1.407	14.59	9.6	6.2	6-7
9.	90	1/9	0.9694	1.357	14.64	9.8	6.15	4-5
10.	100	1/10	0.9740	1.307	14.70	9.0	6.1	3-4

TABLE—2

Emulsion type : O/W ; O/W Ratio = 1 : 3 ; K + T = 5 ml each ; Temp. 30°

Sl. No.	SDSN g	Specific gravity	Viscosity cp	Surface tension (dynes/cm)	Conductivity ($\times 10^{-8}$ ohm $^{-1}$ cm $^{-1}$)	pH	Particle size μ
11.	0.08	0.9486	2.054	14.52	14.5	6.1	3-4
12.	0.04	0.9478	2.151	14.54	15.5	6.2	4-5
13.	0.05	0.9448	2.281	14.52	17.5	6.25	6-7
14.	0.06	0.9428	2.261	14.44	19.5	6.3	6-7
15.	0.07	0.9414	2.280	14.36	22.0	6.3	7-8
16.	0.08	0.9466	2.347	14.27	23.8	6.4	7-8
17.	0.09	0.9397	2.361	14.22	25.0	6.45	8-9
18.	0.10	0.9385	2.380	14.17	26.7	6.5	8-9
19.	0.11	0.9378	2.427	14.11	29.0	6.55	9-10
20.	0.12	0.9369	2.475	14.06	31.0	6.6	10-11

TABLE 3—EMULSION STABILISED BY CATIONIC SURFACTANT

Emulsion type : O/W ; CTMAB = 0.05 g ; K + OO = 5 ml each ; Temp. 30°

Sl. No.	Water ml	Ratio O/W	Specific gravity	Viscosity cp	Surface tension (dynes/cm)	Conductivity ($\times 10^{-8}$ ohm $^{-1}$ cm $^{-1}$)	pH	Particle size μ
1.	10	1/1	0.9289	4.075	13.87	12.5	6.4	11-12
2.	20	1/2	0.9461	2.174	14.03	11.4	6.3	10-11
3.	30	1/3	0.9618	1.449	14.06	11.0	6.25	10-11
4.	40	1/4	0.9660	1.470	14.09	10.7	6.2	9-10
5.	50	1/5	0.9683	1.329	14.13	10.4	6.15	9-10
6.	60	1/6	0.9723	1.308	14.26	10.0	6.1	8-9
7.	70	1/7	0.9731	1.226	14.29	9.1	6.05	8-9
8.	80	1/8	0.9761	1.180	14.35	8.0	6.0	6-7
9.	90	1/9	0.9762	1.149	14.40	7.6	5.95	5-6
10.	100	1/10	0.9809	1.123	14.45	7.2	5.9	4-5

TABLE—4

Emulsion type : O/W ; O/W ratio = 1 : 3 ; K + OO = 5 ml each ; Temp. 30°

Sl. No.	CTMAB g	Specific gravity	Viscosity cp	Surface tension (dynes/cm)	Conductivity ($\times 10^{-8}$ ohm $^{-1}$ cm $^{-1}$)	pH	Particle size μ
11.	0.08	0.9699	1.666	14.21	2.4	6.0	4-5
12.	0.04	0.9674	1.686	14.29	3.6	6.15	6-7
13.	0.05	0.9618	1.702	14.13	4.1	6.2	6-7
14.	0.06	0.9588	1.722	14.09	4.9	6.25	7-8
15.	0.07	0.9554	1.766	14.06	5.8	6.3	7-8
16.	0.08	0.9484	1.806	13.96	6.4	6.35	8-9
17.	0.09	0.9472	1.826	13.98	7.9	6.4	8-9
18.	0.10	0.9436	1.844	13.90	9.1	6.4	9-10
19.	0.11	0.9421	1.891	13.87	11.4	6.45	10-11
20.	0.12	0.9402	2.186	13.83	13.0	6.5	10-11

TABLE 5—EMULSION STABILISED BY NON-IONIC SURFACTANT
Emulsion type : O/W ; Tween-60 = 0.05 g ; T + OO = 5 ml each ; Temp. 30°

Sl. No.	Water ml	Ratio O/W	Specific gravity	Viscosity cp	Surface tension (dynes/cm)	Conductivity ($\times 10^{-5}$ ohm $^{-1}$ cm $^{-1}$)	pH	Particle size μ
1.	10	1/1	0.9251	3.543	13.77	19.0	4.9	11-12
2.	20	1/2	0.9421	2.241	13.90	17.0	5.0	11-12
3.	30	1/3	0.9610	1.421	13.96	12.0	5.05	10-11
4.	40	1/4	0.9625	1.336	14.00	11.0	5.1	10-11
5.	50	1/5	0.9658	1.260	14.06	9.0	5.2	9-10
6.	60	1/6	0.9683	1.201	14.08	7.6	5.2	9-10
7.	70	1/7	0.9703	1.103	14.14	6.4	5.3	8-9
8.	80	1/8	0.9723	1.053	14.16	5.8	5.3	7-8
9.	90	1/9	0.9756	1.004	14.23	3.9	5.4	6-5
10.	100	1/10	0.9774	0.9552	14.27	3.3	5.5	4-5

TABLE—6

Emulsion type : O/W ; O/W ratio = 1 : 3 ; T + OO = 5 ml each ; Temp. 30°

Sl. No.	T-60 g	Specific gravity	Viscosity cp	Surface tension (dynes/cm)	Conductivity ($\times 10^{-5}$ ohm $^{-1}$ cm $^{-1}$)	pH	Particle size μ
1.	0.03	0.9545	1.331	14.22	2.9	7.8	5-6
2.	0.04	0.9526	1.384	14.16	3.2	7.7	6-7
3.	0.05	0.9517	1.440	14.07	3.6	7.65	7-8
4.	0.06	0.9506	1.481	14.04	5.2	7.65	8-9
5.	0.07	0.9478	1.501	13.98	6.4	7.5	9-10
6.	0.08	0.9461	1.521	13.93	7.3	7.45	10-11
7.	0.09	0.9448	1.547	13.89	8.6	7.4	10-11
8.	0.10	0.9428	1.570	13.85	9.9	7.4	11-12
9.	0.11	0.9402	1.614	13.80	11.1	7.35	11-12
10.	0.12	0.9389	1.638	13.76	12.5	7.3	12-13

Results and Discussion

While preparing emulsions it was observed that thick viscous and concentrated emulsions were obtained when oils were added in quantity greater than that of water. This showed the phenomenon of creaming, the rate of which increased with the increase in concentration of oil. Emulsions with minimum water content and/or maximum emulsifying agent concentration were found to be the most stable.

It is evident from Tables 1-6 that surface tension decreases with decrease in the concentration of continuous phase or an increase in the concentration of the emulsifying agent and the lower the surface tension of the emulsion the greater is the stability. Surface tension plays a very important role in the formation of emulsion and maintaining its stability. The surfactant reduces the surface tension between the two phases, decreases the free surface energy of the emulsion formed and produces a stable emulsion. So, as the surface tension decreases the emulsifying power increases. This gives a relationship between surface tension and emulsifier-efficiency of surfactant. Our results are thus in agreement with those of previous workers²¹.

It is also observed from the above data that the viscosity increases as the water ratio decreases

or concentration of surfactant increases and thus the greater the viscosity, the greater is the stability of the emulsion. Viscosity helps emulsification by decreasing the mobility of droplets which forms the dispersed phase and thus retards their approach and coalescence. The globules in dispersed phase are prevented from coalescing and the emulsion system becomes permanent. Neogy and Ghosh²² got similar results with water in benzene emulsion stabilised by Mg-oleate.

In emulsion stabilised by anionic, cationic and nonionic surfactants, it is found that the greater the W/O ratio the lower is the conductivity. It is also found that the greater the concentration of surfactant, the greater is the conductivity of the emulsion.

While determining particle size it was found that the droplet diameters were not uniform practically in all the cases. In each emulsion, globules of maximum diameter were selected and particle size determined. It is concluded from the results that the greater the particle size, the less is the W/O ratio or greater the concentration of surfactant. Thus, a coarse emulsion represents the situation of maximum stability.

In case of anionic and cationic surfactants pH decreases with increase in the concentration of the external phase and increases with the increase of

concentration of surfactant while in the case of nonionic surfactant the reverse is the case.

Specific gravity of emulsion increases with increase in W/O ratio and decreases with increase in emulsifying agent concentration.

It is thus found that the most stable emulsions are formed with lowest surface tension, highest viscosity, maximum droplet diameter, highest conductivity, lowest specific gravity values and slightly acidic solutions.

Acknowledgement

The authors are thankful to Dr. M. R. Sharma, Head, Botany Dept. and to the authorities of D.A.V. (P. G.) College, Dehra Dun for facilities.

References

1. J. T. KENNEY, *Chem. Abs.*, 1974, **81**, 127103.
2. J. E. CHARLES and G. W. HALLWORTH, *J. Colloid Interface Sci.*, 1963, **26**, 75.
3. P. H. ELWORTHY and A. T. FLORENCE, *J. Pharm. Pharmacol., Suppl.*, 1967, **19**, 140.
4. P. BECHER, *J. Colloid Interface Sci.*, 1967, **24**, 91.
5. I. I. CONRAD, *J. Soc. Cosmetic Chemists*, 1954, **5**, 11.
6. R. L. WHISTLER and J. N. BRILLER, "Industrial Gums", Academic Press, New York, 1959.
7. J. H. SCHULMAN, *J. Lefa. Trans. Faraday Soc.*, 1954, **50**, 598.
8. L. N. MUKHERJEE and O. P. GUPTA, *Indian J. Appl. Chem.*, 1968, **31**, 90.
9. L. NARASINHA RAO and V. SUBBA RAO, *Indian J. Pharm.*, 1967, **29**, 182.
10. W. SCHEUK, *Ger. (East) Patent*, 52, 21 Dec. 15, 1966.
11. L. N. MUKHERJEE and S. D. SHUKLA, *Indian J. Appl. Chem.*, 1967, **30**, 17.
12. RASSER, *Oel. Markt.*, 1926, **8**, 245.
13. O. E. ARAUJO, *J. Pharmisci*, 1967, **56**, 1141.
14. L. N. MUKHERJEE and S. D. SHUKLA, *Indian J. Appl. Chem.*, 1965, **28**, 177.
15. E. W. MAURER, A. J. STIRTAN and J. K. WEIL, *U. S. Patent*, 32917 0, Dec. 13, 1966.
16. L. H. BERGER A. REING and G. SAURWALD, *Ger. Offen.*, 1916283, *Chem. Abs.*, 1970, **73**, 184242w.
17. MCELROY, *U. S. Patent*, 1444844, Feb. 13, 1923.
18. K. D. JAIN and M. K. SHARMA, *J. Indian Chem. Soc.*, 1970, **47**, 989.
19. P. BOCHER, "Emulsions: Theory and Practice", Reinhold Publishing Corp., New York, 1966. p. 267.
20. E. A. HAUSER and J. E. LYNN, "Experiments in Colloid Chemistry", McGraw-Hill Book Co., N. Y., 1940, p. 129.
21. C. P. SHILLABAR. "Photomicrography in Theory and Practice", John Wiley and Sons, Inc., N. Y., 1949, p. 41.
22. R. K. NEOGY and B. N. GHOSH, *J. Indian Chem. Soc.*, 1953, **30**, 113.